

Securing Science Gateways

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Abstract—Gateways provide access to computational codes as a service to their users. One popular design pattern is to use a single user account on an HPC system to run all workloads for the gateway’s user community. This introduces several security concerns for the owner of the user account, the machine, and the integrity of the workloads run by the gateway. In this paper we present preliminary work on the Everglades Shell (`evshell`), a limited, secure Linux shell that runs in user space. We begin by discussing the use case `evshell` addresses. Next we discuss how it fills a gap in the existing secure shell landscape. We then describe `evshell`’s design and usage within a gateway context before concluding with areas of future work.

I. INTRODUCTION

One form of Science Gateway is a system that allows a scientific modeling code to run on a high performance compute (HPC) resource through a shared “community” account. The concept is to allow a large number of people to explore the possible outputs of a model, but without conferring a large degree of trust.

The Agave [1], Airvata [2], and Tapis [3] frameworks provide a kind of scientific middleware, a RESTful JSON API to facilitate creation of gateways that fit the above model. While they are far from the only tools in this space, the security issues faced by a person deploying an application using this framework are common.

Typically, these tools connect to a compute resource via `ssh` and run commands through `bash`. If correctly configured, these tools grant limited access to users, usually the ability to run a single type of calculation. Unsurprisingly, it is possible to inadvertently create security loopholes through misconfiguration, so it is important to carefully read the documentation for the framework you are using and spend time thinking about what issues might exist.

The authors and maintainers of these gateway frameworks take great care to keep their systems secure. Prior efforts by XSEDE and the SGCI have produced guidelines with best practices for securing a community user account for use by a gateway [4]. However, despite the best efforts of gateway personnel, security breaches are bound to occur. It therefore makes sense to limit the access of each actor involved in running the gateway application code.

We also note that there are far fewer resources for self-service application publishers, and it is likely a matter of time until an account on one or more servers become compromised.

For this reason, it is desirable to limit the access a gateway user has to commands within a `bash` environment in much in the way ‘`sudo`’ restricts access to root commands. This paper

describes preliminary work on `evshell`, a restricted Linux shell, written in Python, that runs in user space.

II. MOTIVATION

Many solutions exist to restrict and/or secure runtime environments. Gateways commonly use OCI [5]-compliant container runtimes (Docker, `runc`, `crun`, `runv`, etc) to encapsulate an application, then further restrict the container’s permissions through the use of AppArmor, `seccomp`, or SELinux [6]. In this paper we focus on HPC environments, which tend not to natively support OCI container runtimes due to the privilege escalation required to start a container [7]. Singularity containers are popular with HPC operators due to their enforcement of user space restrictions [8]. This, however, requires Singularity to be installed and available to the shared user account.

Restricted shells exist in `Bash`, `Zsh`, `Fish`, and others [9], but require per-account configuration and prohibit behaviors that are necessary, such as changing directory and redirecting output. The Community Shell application (`commsh`) is another take on a restricted shell focused on gateway use cases [10]. It provides a flexible DSL to whitelist allowed commands, and a plugin architecture allowing callouts to perform custom audit activity. This lends itself particularly well to scenarios where a single user account is being used to perform actions on behalf of one or more unknown external principals [11]. It is, in fact, very similar to `evshell`, both in its purpose and implementation. We believe, however, that `evshell` has a number of advantages. We list them below.

Despite the utility of `commsh`, and the increased security restricted shells in general provide, they have yet to gain broad adoption within the gateway community. Anecdotal evidence points to the lack of administrative control the gateways have to install and configure the desired behavior over the HPC resources as one prominent reason. However, a full discussion of this topic is beyond the scope of this paper.

III. DESCRIPTION

In this paper, we introduce `evshell` [12], an implementation of the shell in Python. `evshell` is implemented as an executable module. It can be invoked in its vanilla form as a pass through shell, or imported as a module and extended by overriding the Python functions listed in Table 1. In our experiments, `evshell` is invoked through the `command=` mechanism provided by `ssh`’s `authorized_keys` file (note that it is not necessary to install it as a default shell for any account). This allows us to limit the restricted shell interface to those users logging in via specific `ssh` keys. Gateway maintainers will still have full and regular `bash` access.

TABLE I
THE LIST OF EXTENSIBLE FUNCTIONS AVAILABLE IN EVSHELL. BY
DEFAULT ALL RETURN TRUE.

Function Name	Description
<code>allow_cd</code>	Restrict changing directories
<code>allow_cmd</code>	which command or command options may be run
<code>allow_read</code>	Restrict which files may be read via the shell's input redirection (<) mechanism
<code>allow_write</code>	Restrict which files may be written via the shell's output redirection (>) mechanism
<code>allow_append</code>	Restricts which files may be written via the shell's output append (>>) mechanism
<code>allow_set_var</code>	Restricts which environment variables may be written
<code>allow_access_var</code>	Restricts which environment variables may be read

We made the decision to use functions rather than the standard white/black list, or the DSL approach used by `commsh`, to allow maximum flexibility in crafting the the security measures required for an individual gateway or application. This affords the opportunity to leverage callouts to system utilities, policy engines, and even additional security tools. Utilizing functions also affords the opportunity to ensure things like checksum validation and environment variable precedence are maintained prior to command invocation.

There is no limit to the custom logic that can be implemented via this mechanism. In particular, limitations of the `commsh` with regard to restrictions within a community account can be implemented. To accomplish this, one could create a variable, e.g., `COMM_USER` and only allow it to be set once. It could be set in in the `allowed_keys` file used by `ssh` or some gateway-framework-specific mechanism and could be checked by each of the `allow_*` functions above to limit which directories and files could be read/written.

A. SFTP-server integration

Some gateways, e.g., Agave and Tapis, make heavy use of the `sftp-server` file in addition to `bash`. The unrestricted use of the `sftp-server` command would potentially invalidate the limitations imposed by such tools as `commsh` or `evshell`.

For this reason, the `allow_cmd` may (optionally) return a new command line rather than the one the shell asks for. Using this mechanism, `evshell` can replace `/usr/libexec/openssh/sftp-server` with something else, e.g.

`/home/community-user/openssh/sftp-server`, a locally compiled version of the `sftp-server`. We have implemented a modification of `sftp-server` which calls Python in a manner similar to what is done in `evshell` [13], i.e., it calls methods such as `access_open`, `access_mkdir`, etc. The structure of the `sftp-server` code made this modification straightforward.

Obviously, any use of a custom `sftp-server` should be done in cooperation with systems administrators, especially if the user account is running on a system advertising any kind of security compliance. Use of alternative software dependencies, port exposure, cryptography libraries, etc. could compromise the system's compliance and introduce unnecessary risk to its owners. While the custom `sftp-server` fork mentioned in this paper satisfies the requirements of our initial use cases, it was modified in close communication with our systems administrators to ensure additional risks were not introduced.

B. Limitations

Due to `evshell` running in user space, there are several limitations of which potential adopters should be aware. First, `evshell` is, fundamentally, a preventative agent, operating at the application level rather than the kernel. As such, it cannot intercept system calls, or trace binary execution to predict and prevent prevent undesirable actions. Thus, `evshell` can prevent a binary invocation, but cannot prevent those binaries from taking additional action. Any action a binary takes after launched will fall back on standard linux security for the invoking user account. Similarly, `evshell` cannot restrict IO access from within a command's invocation other than to restrict the use of fully resolved paths in the command path and argument list that do not match it's `allow_*` rules.

`evshell` also does not currently track any processes spawned by the commands it runs. Thus, if `evshell` calls a binary does not clean up after itself cleanly before exiting, then `evshell` will not be aware of the abandoned processes, and could exit having contributed to the creation of zombie processes. While the abandoned processes would not directly be the fault of `evshell`, the possibility still exists and should be accounted for through proper application profiling and interrupt signal handling similarly to what one would do in a containerized environment using `tini`.

Finally, while `evshell` will sanitize and resolve paths within the commands it invokes, recursion is allowed. Because `evshell` is a python utility, it is subject to the same recursion limits as any other python application. As such, applications legitimately pushing this limit should take appropriate precautions.

Implementing a correct security protocol that doesn't interfere with normal gateway operations requires careful thought. However, it is possible to run a gateway with `evshell` (and modified `scp/ssh/sftp-server`) without imposing any access restrictions in order to collect logs to study its normal commands and requests. It is important for those responsible for adding and maintaining gateway applications to take the time to observe their application's behavior via `evshell`'s logging mechanism, monitoring file and command access patterns, and examining process tree traces. Having this information should make it much easier to implement the desired security measures.

IV. EXAMPLES

In our initial development of the `evshell`, we worked with a “hello world” application in Tapis, a simple call to `/bin/echo`. This already exercised many of the features of the gateway service. Once we had enough bash features in place for that to run correctly, we tried running a SWAN application [14], an application that we have used in other gateway research. No additional modification of `evshell` turned out to be necessary in order to get this application to run. The appropriate input files were transferred, the executables run with MPI, and the output was collected.

Note that to properly limit commands run through MPI, either the default ssh key used to connect from one host to another needs to also invoke `evshell`, or access to the `mpirun`, `ssh`, `scp`, etc. commands need to be limited, otherwise the restrictions of `evshell` can be circumvented.

Next we turned to an entirely different framework, Airvata. LSU had an Airvata installation pre-installed for test purposes with a handful of built-in applications. One of which was LAMMPS [15]. While Airvata accesses a machine in much the same way as Tapis/Agave, i.e. it uses a combination of `bash` and `sftp-server` commands, it is an entirely different product built by independent researchers. Substitution of `bash` with `evshell` did not impact the running of LAMMPS through Airvata. No additional modification of `evshell` was necessary to successfully run this application.

While `evshell` is not fully bash-compliant and is not yet usable as a replacement of `bash` for daily work activities, the demands of a gateway are more limited in scope and easier to satisfy.

V. CONCLUSION

`evshell` is a limited Linux shell that runs in user space. Currently, gateway frameworks are given complete access to an account and can do anything a regular user would do. While we are unaware of any particular breaches in gateway servers, one is bound to occur eventually, and we believe it only makes sense to limit the access of such systems to the minimum necessary to perform the task they were designed for. We note that `evshell` accomplishes this without the need to change the gateway frameworks in any way. As long as the commands the gateway issues follow the pattern that is expected of them, `evshell` will not deny their requests.

We have successfully used `evshell` to run both (1) a SWAN application [14] using the Tapis framework, and (2) a LAMMPS application [15] using the Airvata framework. Though these applications are minimal, they are real science applications and exercise all of the basic features of the `evshell`, including the `sftp-server` command intercept.

`evshell` provides several attractive features such as data, binary, environment, and permission whitelisting, path resolution, and proper capture of `stdin` and `stdout`. Future areas of work include subprocess cleanup, automatic instrumentation of spawned processes, and standardized logging output.

We note that no gateway or shared account setup should be implemented on any resource without discussing such

measures with the administrators of the system. Regardless of what security measures are implemented, the people who are responsible for the integrity of the machine need to be intimately involved.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Rion Dooley, Steven R. Brandt, and John Fonner, “The Agave Platform: An Open, Science-as-a-Service Platform for Digital Science,” in *Proceedings of the 2018 Practice & Experience in Advanced Research Computing*. Pittsburgh, PA: ACM, Jul. 2018.
- [2] S. Marru, L. Gunathilake, C. Herath, P. Tangchaisin, M. Pierce, C. Mattmann, R. Singh, T. Gunarathne, E. Chinthaka, R. Gardler, A. Slominski, A. Douma, S. Perera, and S. Weerawarana, “Apache Airvata: A Framework for Distributed Applications and Computational Workflows,” in *Proceedings of the 2011 ACM Workshop on Gateway Computing Environments*, ser. GCE ’11. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2011, pp. 21–28. [Online]. Available: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2110486.2110490>
- [3] J. Stubbs, R. Cardone, M. Packard, A. Jamthe, S. Padhy, S. Terry, J. Looney, J. Meiring, S. Black, M. Dahan, S. Cleveland, and G. Jacobs, “Tapis: An API Platform for Reproducible, Distributed Computational Research,” in *Advances in Information and Communication*, K. Arai, Ed. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021, vol. 1363, pp. 878–900, series Title: Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing. [Online]. Available: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-030-73100-7_61
- [4] “Gateways for Developers and Operators - XSEDE.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.xsede.org/ecosystem/science-gateways/gateways-for-developers>
- [5] “Open Container Initiative Runtime Specification,” Jun. 2022, original-date: 2015-06-05T23:30:10Z. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/opencontainers/runtime-spec>
- [6] “runc/SPEC.md at main · opencontainers/runc.” [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/opencontainers/runc>
- [7] “Singularity and Docker — Singularity container 2.6 documentation.” [Online]. Available: https://sylabs.io/guides/2.6/user-guide/singularity_and_docker.html
- [8] G. M. Kurtzer, V. Sochat, and M. W. Bauer, “Singularity: Scientific containers for mobility of compute,” *PLOS ONE*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 1–20, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0177459>
- [9] “Restricted shell,” Dec. 2021, page Version ID: 1060812921. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Restricted_shell&oldid=1060812921
- [10] “Restricted community accounts: Securing science gateways at the account level,” in *Proceedings of the 2006 TeraGrid Conference*, 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://security.ncsa.illinois.edu/research/commacct/docs/papers/teragrid06.pdf>
- [11] T. Fleury, “Restricting Community Accounts using the Community Shell (commsh),” Jun. 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://security.ncsa.illinois.edu/research/commacct/docs/howto.html>
- [12] S. Brandt, “Everglades shell source code,” Oct. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/stevenrbrandt/evshell>
- [13] —, “Modified portable OpenSSH,” Jun. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/stevenrbrandt/openssh-portable>
- [14] N. Booi, R. C. Ris, and L. H. Holthuisen, “A third-generation wave model for coastal regions: 1. model description and validation,” *Journal of geophysical research: Oceans*, vol. 104, no. C4, pp. 7649–7666, 1999.
- [15] A. P. Thompson, H. M. Aktulga, R. Berger, D. S. Bolintineanu, W. M. Brown, P. S. Crozier, P. J. in’t Veld, A. Kohlmeyer, S. G. Moore, T. D. Nguyen *et al.*, “Lammps-a flexible simulation tool for particle-based materials modeling at the atomic, meso, and continuum scales,” *Computer Physics Communications*, vol. 271, p. 108171, 2022.